

1 **Reversed phase liquid chromatography for the enantioseparation of local**
2 **anaesthetics in polysaccharide-based stationary phases. Application to**
3 **biodegradability studies**

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12 **ABSTRACT**

13 A comprehensive study on the chiral separation of bupivacaine, mepivacaine,
14 prilocaine and propanocaine with eight commercial polysaccharide-based chiral
15 stationary phases (CSPs) in reversed phase conditions compatible with MS detection is
16 performed. Methanol and acetonitrile are used as organic modifiers. Retention and
17 resolution values obtained for each compound in the different CSPs and mobile phases
18 are compared. The polysaccharide-based CSPs tested present different
19 enantioselectivity towards the analytes. From the results, the experimental conditions
20 for determining the enantiomers of bupivacaine, mepivacaine, prilocaine and
21 propanocaine in saline aqueous samples using MS detection are used, for the first time,
22 to perform an enantioselective biodegradability study.

23 **Keywords:** local anaesthetics; cellulose and amylose-based chiral stationary phases,
24 reversed phase conditions, enantioselective biodegradation study.

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29 **1. Introduction**

30 Local anaesthetics are one of the most used analgesics. They are drugs that
31 reversibly inhibit the production and conduction of the stimulus of any excitable
32 membrane, particularly in nerve tissue. This action is used to produce loss of pain
33 sensitivity in a particular area of the body. Adverse effects are infrequent; however,
34 their systemic toxicity can result in serious patient harm, including seizure, cardiac
35 compromise and death [1,2].

36 Local anaesthetics have in their molecular structure a lipophilic aromatic ring, an
37 intermediate ester or amide linkage and a tertiary amine, which are responsible for the
38 clinical properties of the molecule [1]. Furthermore, some local anesthetics are chiral
39 and their enantiomers show significant differences in pharmacological and toxicological
40 properties. Thus, (*R*)-bupivacaine shows greater potency and toxicity in the
41 cardiovascular and central nervous systems than (*S*)-bupivacaine. The enantiomers of
42 prilocaine also show different toxicity. It has been found that the (*S*)-prilocaine
43 enantiomer is the most toxic and the hepatic clearance of (*R*)-prilocaine is greater [3].

44 High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with chiral stationary phases
45 (CSPs) is widely used for the separation of chiral compounds. Among the large number
46 of CSPs commercially available the polysaccharide-based chiral stationary phases are

47 one of most commonly used, due to their broad applicability [4,5]. Separations with
48 these CSPs are normally carrying out in normal and polar organic conditions and less
49 frequently in reversed phase conditions [5]. Reversed phase conditions are adequate for
50 chiral separation of polar compounds as well as for the analysis of aqueous matrix
51 samples (e.g. biological and environmental samples), and can be compatible with MS
52 detection if the usual non-volatile additives (e.g. hexafluorophosphate, phosphate
53 buffers) or suppress analyte response (e.g. diethylamine) are avoided.

54 The separation of the enantiomers of local anaesthetics has been performed
55 using polysaccharide-based CSPs in both normal and polar organic conditions [6-12].
56 However, as far as we know, only two applications on the use of reversed conditions
57 have been reported for the separation of bupivacaine [13] and mepivacaine enantiomers
58 [14]. The separation of bupivacaine enantiomers was achieved using cellulose tris(3,5-
59 dimethylphenylcarbamate) and a mobile phase consisting of a mixture of methanol: 20
60 mM ammonium bicarbonate buffer 70:30 with 0.1% of diethylamine. For mepivacaine
61 enantiomers, the use of immobilized cellulose tris(3,5-dichlorophenylcarbamate) and a
62 mobile phase consisting of a mixture of acetonitrile: 20 mM ammonium bicarbonate
63 buffer 35:65 was proposed. No references were found in the literature for the other local
64 anaesthetics under study (prilocaine and propanocaine).

65 Nowadays, the presence of drugs in the environment is a big issue because of the
66 possible impact of these compounds not only in human health but also in the
67 environment [15,16]. Of special concern is the occurrence of chiral drugs whose
68 enantiomers may have different toxicological and ecotoxicological properties compared
69 to each other [17-19]. They can be present in the environment in different proportions as
70 a result of the enantioselective human metabolism, and also of the microbial
71 biodegradation during the wastewater treatment process. In this context, the

72 quantification of enantiomeric fraction (*EF*) during enantioselective studies about
73 biodegradation is crucial for environmental risk assessment [20-22].

74 Local anesthetics are ubiquitous compounds in the environment due to their high
75 hospital use [23]. In fact, the presence in wastewater of mepivacaine, lidocaine
76 bupivacaine, prilocaine, procaine and benzocaine in concentrations in the ng L⁻¹ level
77 has been reported [24,25]. Nevertheless, there are no references in the literature about
78 the possible enantioselective biodegradation of local anesthetics.

79 In this paper a systematic study on the chiral separation of the local anaesthetics
80 bupivacaine, mepivacaine, prilocaine and propanocaine using five cellulose based CSPs,
81 (Lux® Cellulose 1, Lux® Cellulose 2, Lux® Cellulose 3, Lux® Cellulose 4 and
82 immobilised Lux® Cellulose 5) and three amylose based CSPs (Lux® Amylose 1,
83 Lux® Amylose 2 and immobilised Lux® Amylose 3), under reversed phase conditions
84 compatible with MS detection is performed. Methanol and acetonitrile were used as
85 organic modifiers. Retention and resolution values obtained for each compound in the
86 different CSPs and mobile phases were compared. As far as we know, it is the first time
87 that this kind of study is performed in the current experimental conditions. From the
88 resolution values and the chromatographic retention times obtained the experimental
89 conditions for determining the enantiomers of bupivacaine, mepivacaine, prilocaine and
90 propanocaine in aqueous samples using MS detection were proposed. These conditions
91 were applied to evaluate for the first time the biodegradability of bupivacaine,
92 mepivacaine, prilocaine and propanocaine enantiomers according to the OECD ready
93 biodegradability test [26,27].

94

95 **2. Material and methods**

96 2.1. Chemicals and solutions

97 Racemic bupivacaine (BUPI) was from Cayman Chemical Co (Ann Arbor, MI,
98 USA) and (*S*)-bupivacaine hydrochloride (*S*-BUPI) was from Sigma-Aldrich (©Merck
99 KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany). The rest of drugs tested were kindly donated by several
100 pharmaceutical laboratories: fluoxetine hydrochloride (FLX) by Alter (Madrid, Spain);
101 racemic mepivacaine hydrochloride (MEPI) and racemic prilocaine hydrochloride
102 (PRILO) by Laboratorios Inibsa (Barcelona, Spain) and racemic propanocaine
103 (PROPA) by Laboratorio Seid (Barcelona, Spain).

104 All reagents were of analytical grade. Ammonium acetate, ammonium
105 bicarbonate, ammonium hydroxide, sodium azide, acetonitrile (ACN) and methanol
106 (MeOH) (®Multisolvent, HPLC grade) were from Scharlau, S.L. (Barcelona, Spain). 5
107 mM ammonium bicarbonate buffer solution was prepared by dissolving the appropriate
108 amount of ammonium bicarbonate in water and adjusting the pH to 8.0 with 1 M
109 ammonium hydroxide. Ammonium acetate buffer solution (10 mM, pH 8.0) was
110 prepared in the same way from ammonium acetate. Ultra Clear TWF UV ultrapure
111 water (SG Water, Barsbüttel, Germany) was used to prepare solutions. Binary mixtures
112 consisting of different percentages of acetonitrile or methanol and ammonium
113 bicarbonate buffer (5 mM, pH 8) (10-100 % in volume of ACN or 30-90 % in volume
114 of MeOH) were tested as mobile phases for the separation of the chiral compounds. For
115 the determination of FLX a mixture consisting of acetonitrile: ammonium acetate buffer
116 (10 mM, pH 8.0) (60:40, v/v) was prepared as mobile phase.

117 The minimal salts medium (MSM) solution used in the biodegradability assays
118 was prepared as previously described in references [21,22]. Activated sludge was kindly
119 donated by General de Análisis Materiales y Servicios, S.L (GAMASER, S.L.,
120 Valencia, Spain). It was collected from the aerated tanks of the Quart Benàger WWTP

121 (Valencia, Spain) [21,22] in plastic flasks and stored at 5 °C until usage. The storage
122 time was lower than 24 h.

123 Stock standard solutions of 1000 mg L⁻¹ of BUPI, MEPI, PRILO, PROPA and
124 FLX were prepared by dissolving the adequate amount of each compound in MeOH. To
125 prepare the calibration standards, intermediate stock solutions of 100 mg L⁻¹ of BUPI, -
126 MEPI, PRILO, PROPA and FLX were prepared by dilution of the corresponding 1000
127 mg L⁻¹ stock solution in MeOH. For each drug, calibration solutions in the
128 concentration range 1-30 mg L⁻¹ were prepared by dilution of the corresponding
129 intermediate stock solution of 100 mg L⁻¹ in the MSM. 10 mg L⁻¹ of *S*-BUPI in MSM
130 was also prepared for the identification of the enantiomer peaks of BUPI. For the
131 biodegradability assays, working solutions of approximately 20 mg L⁻¹ of BUPI, MEPI,
132 PRILO, PROPA and FLX were prepared by dilution of the 1000 mg L⁻¹ stock solution
133 in the MSM. The solutions were stored under refrigeration at 5 °C until usage.

134 2.2. Instrumentation

135 An Agilent Technologies 1100 chromatograph (Palo Alto, CA, USA) equipped
136 with a binary pump, an UV-visible diode array detector, a mass spectrometer with a
137 source of electrospray and atmospheric pressure chemical ionisation (ESI / APCI) and
138 single quadrupole, a column thermostat and an autosampler was used. Data acquisition
139 and processing were performed using the LC/MSD ChemStation software (B.04.02 SP1
140 [208], ©Agilent Technologies 2001-2010).

141 For the determination of FLX, an Halo C18 column (2.7 µm, 75 × 4.6 mm i.d.;
142 Advanced Materials Technology, Wilmington, USA) was used. For the separation of
143 the local anaesthetics enantiomers, eight polysaccharide-based chiral stationary phases
144 were tested: Lux® Cellulose-1 (cellulose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate); 3 µm, 150

145 × 4.6 mm i.d.; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA); Lux® Cellulose-2 (cellulose tris(3-
146 chloro-4-methylphenylcarbamate); 3 µm, 150 × 4.6 mm i.d.; Phenomenex); Lux®
147 Cellulose-3 (cellulose tris(4-methylbenzoate); 3 µm, 150 × 4.6 mm i.d.; Phenomenex);
148 Lux® Cellulose-4 (cellulose tris(4-chloro-3-methylphenylcarbamate); 3 µm, 150 × 4.6
149 mm i.d.; Phenomenex); immobilised Lux® Cellulose-5 (cellulose tris (3,5-
150 dichlorophenylcarbamate); 3 µm, 150 × 4.6 mm i.d.; Phenomenex); Lux® Amylose-1
151 (amylose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate); 3 µm, 150 × 4.6 mm i.d.; Phenomenex);
152 Lux® Amylose-2 (amylose tris(5-chloro-2- methylphenylcarbamate); 3 µm, 150 × 2.0
153 mm i.d.; Phenomenex) and immobilised Lux® Amylose-3 (amylose tris(3-chloro-5-
154 methylphenylcarbamate); 3 µm, 150 × 4.6 mm i.d.; Phenomenex).

155 The mobile phase flow rate was 1.0 mL min⁻¹ in all cases except for the Lux®
156 Amylose-2. In this last column, the mobile phase flow rate was set at 0.5 mL min⁻¹. The
157 separation temperature was set at 25 °C for fluoxetine and local anaesthetics. In some
158 cases, temperatures of 15 and 40 °C were also assayed to improve the resolution of the
159 enantiomers. The injection volume was 2 µL and the detection was performed in the UV
160 at 220 nm.

161 In the mass detector, positive ESI mode was chosen under the following
162 conditions: voltage, 3000 V; nebuliser pressure, 35 psig; N₂ flow, 12 L min⁻¹; drying
163 temperature 350 °C. The total current ion chromatogram (TIC) with the mass/charge
164 ratio range (*m/z*) of 100-500 was recorded. The selected ion monitoring mode (SIM),
165 which corresponds to the [M+H]⁺ ion for each compound, was recorded too at the *m/z*
166 values 289.2, 247.2, 221.2 and 312.2 for BUPI, MEPI, PRILO and PROPA,
167 respectively.

168 For the preparation of sample mixtures, 15 mL conical sterile polypropylene
169 tubes (Deltalab, S.L., Barcelona, Spain) were used. Disposable sterile filter pipette tips

170 (Capp Expell, Odense, Denmark) were also used. For the biodegradability assays, a
171 shaking incubator with temperature control (WiseCube®Wis-30, Witeg Labortechnik
172 GmbH, Wetheim, Germany) was used. Prior to the measurement of the microbial
173 growth, incubated samples were subjected to agitation in a vortex mixer (Velp Scientific
174 Vortex, Usmate, Italy). Microbial growth was monitored by measuring the optical
175 density of the cultures at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀) with an Epoch 2 microplate reader (Biotek
176 Instruments Inc., Vermont, USA) and 96-well plates with UV transparent flat bottom
177 (Corning, Kennebunk, ME, USA). Samples were stored at -80 °C in an ultra-low
178 temperature freezer (U570 Premium, New Brunswick Scientific, Herts, UK) until
179 chromatographic analysis.

180 Prior to injection into the chromatographic system, analyte solutions were
181 filtered through disposable 0.22 µm Nylon® syringe filters (Análisis Vínicos, S.L.,
182 Tomelloso, Ciudad Real, Spain). Mobile phase solutions were vacuum-filtered through
183 0.22 µm Nylon® membranes (Micron Separations, Westboro, MA, USA) and were
184 degassed in an Elmasonic S60 ultrasonic bath (Elma, Singen, Germany) prior to use. A
185 Crison MicropH 2000 pHmeter (Crison Instruments, Barcelona, Spain) was employed
186 to adjust the pH of the buffer solutions.

187 *2.3. Biodegradability assays*

188 The biodegradability assays were performed in batch mode at approximately 20
189 mg L⁻¹ BUPI, MEPI, PRILO and PROPA. The incubation times of samples mixtures
190 were prefixed a $t = 0, 3, 7, 14$ and 28 days. The procedure followed to perform the
191 biodegradability assays was similar to that used in previous papers [22]. In the present
192 paper, sodium azide was added to prevent non-desirable microbial growth. In the abiotic
193 assays, 0.1 % NaN₃ solution in ultrapure water was used instead of the activated sludge
194 to prepare sample mixtures. In the biotic assays, a small amount of NaN₃ was added to

195 sample mixtures after incubation to stop the microbial activity. Biodegradability assays
196 for FLX at 20 mg L⁻¹ were also performed to control inoculum activity [28] in parallel
197 to those of local anaesthetics.

198

199 2.4. Calculations. Direct chromatographic approach

200 The values of biodegradation, BD , were calculated directly from the
201 chromatographic information (peak area, A) according to a direct chromatographic
202 approach recently published [22]:

$$BD = \frac{S_0 - S}{S_0} \times 100 = \frac{A_0 - A}{A_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

203 where S is the concentration data obtained over time, S_0 is the initial concentration and A_0
204 represents the area obtained at $t = 0$.

205 The enantiomeric fraction (EF) at each incubation time was calculated either
206 directly from the chromatographic peak area or using the concentration data obtained
207 for each enantiomer [22]:

$$EF = \frac{S_{E1}}{S_{E1} + S_{E2}} = \frac{A_{E1}}{A_{E1} + A_{E2}} \quad (2)$$

208 Where E1 and E2 represent the less and the most retained enantiomers, respectively.

209 For the estimation of the BD following this direct chromatographic approach it is
210 assumed that the intercept (b_0) of the calibration lines of both enantiomers are equal to
211 0, i.e. statistically non-significant (logical situation in the absence of systematic error).
212 To estimate EF values the assumption that the slopes (b_1) are statistically equal should
213 also be met [22].

214

215 **3. Results and discussion**

216 *3.1. Chiral chromatographic separation*

217 The use of different polysaccharide-based CSPs in reversed phase conditions
218 compatible with MS detection (i.e. aqueous-organic mobile phases in the absence of
219 non-volatile reagents) for the separation of the enantiomers of local anaesthetics was
220 investigated. Aqueous-organic mobile phases are preferable in the present study because
221 of their compatibility with the saline aqueous matrix samples involved in the
222 biodegradability assays. Table 1 shows the chemical structure, the molecular weight,
223 M_r , the acidity constant, pK_a , the logarithm of the *n*-octanol-water partition coefficient,
224 $\log P$, and the $\log D$ ($\log P$ estimated at pH 8.0) for the studied compounds. At the
225 working *pH* the compounds present positive charge (BUPI +0.55, MEPI +0.33, PRILO
226 +0.44 and PROPA +0.25) and variable hydrophobic character ($\log D$ values range
227 between 1.6 and 4.5).

228 For the separation of enantiomers of BUPI, MEPI, PRILO and PROPA five
229 commercial cellulose-based CSPs [Lux® Cellulose-1 (Cell1), Lux® Cellulose-2
230 (Cell2), Lux® Cellulose-3 (Cell3), Lux® Cellulose-4 (Cell4) and Lux® Cellulose-5
231 (Cell5)] and three commercial amylose-based CSPs [Lux® Amylose-1 (Am1), Lux®
232 Amylose-2 (Am2) and Lux® Amylose-3 (Am3)] (see experimental section) were tested.
233 Several binary mixtures consisting of ammonium bicarbonate buffer (5 mM, pH 8) and
234 different proportions of ACN (10-100%, v/v) or MeOH (30-90%, v/v) were assayed as
235 mobile phases.

236 Tables 2 and 3 show the chromatographic data (retention and resolution data)
237 obtained for BUPI, MEPI, PRILO and PROPA in all the reversed mobile phases

238 assayed using cellulose and amylose-based chiral stationary phases, respectively. As can
239 be observed, the separation results obtained for local anesesthetics in acetonitrile and
240 methanol mobile phases were quite different.

241 When MeOH was used as organic modifier, for all the columns and compounds,
242 retention decreased as the proportion of the organic modifier in the mobile phase
243 increased (typical reverse-phase behavior). This behaviour has been previously reported
244 for other compounds [4-5]. Methanol is a protic solvent and may compete with the
245 analyte for hydrogen-bond interactions with the polysaccharide-based CSPs. The
246 addition of water to methanol did not alter hydrogen-bond interactions, but hydrophobic
247 interactions increase and therefore retention increase [4-5].

248 For aqueous-MeOH mobile phases, a linear trend between the logarithm of
249 retention factors for the less retained enantiomers and their corresponding $\log D$ values
250 for each CSP studied was observed, indicating that hydrophobicity of compounds plays
251 a key role in the retention (e.g. PROPA was the most retained according to its $\log D$).

252 When ACN was used as organic modifier, for all the columns and compounds,
253 the retention of compounds initially decrease for low water content in the mobile phase
254 (HILIC behavior). while at the higher content (up to 20 %(v/v) of water content) in the
255 mobile phase retention increase (reverse-phase behavior). This behaviour has been
256 explained taking into account that, ACN, as a non-hydrogen-bond donor solvent, allows
257 more hydrogen-bond interactions between the chiral analyte and the polysaccharide-
258 based CSPs. The addition of water to the mobile phase provokes two opposite
259 contributions in the retention of analytes. On one hand, water competes with analytes
260 for hydrogen-bond interactions with the polysaccharide-based-CSPs and reduces the
261 analyte retention (HILIC like behavior). On the other hand, water promotes
262 hydrophobic interactions between the analyte and the polysaccharide-based-CSPs and

263 increases the analyte retention (reverse-phase like behavior) [4-5]. The explained effect
264 is more evident for the column Cell3, Cell5 and Am1 for MEPI and PROPA.

265 Among the cellulose-based CSPs, the immobilised column Cell5 showed the
266 highest retention values for all the studied compounds. In the case of amylose-based
267 CSPs, the immobilised column Am3 showed the highest retention values for all the
268 studied compounds .

269 The polysaccharide-based CSPs tested presented different enantioselectivity
270 towards the analytes. As shown in Tables 2 and 3, in the conditions assayed, a single
271 column was unable to completely resolve ($R_s > 1.5$) the enantiomers of the four studied
272 compounds. The Cell2 CSP provided the best enantioselectivity, being able to resolve
273 three of the four compounds under study (MEPI, PRILO and PROPA). The Cell4
274 allowed the resolution of two of the analytes (PRILO and PROPA), whereas the Cell3,
275 Cell5 and Am1 CSPs only allowed the enantioseparation of one of the compounds
276 (BUPI, MEPI and PRILO, respectively). The Cell1, Am2 and Am3 CSPs did not
277 provide the complete resolution of any of the local anaesthetics, only the partial
278 resolution of some of them. From the results, and in the experimental conditions tested,
279 the cellulose-based CSPs showed better enantioselectivity towards the four analytes
280 than the amylose-based CSPs.

281 The enantioselectivity of Cell2 and Cell4 for all the compounds was similar,
282 although the resolution was generally better in Cell2. The only difference between these
283 two stationary phases is the position of the chlorine and methyl substituents in the
284 phenylcarbamate moieties. The Cell1 CSP contains two methyl groups in the positions 3
285 and 5 in the phenylcarbamate ring whereas the Cell5 has two chlorine atoms in these
286 positions. As can be observed in Table 2, the R_s values obtained in Cell5 were in
287 general better than in Cell1, especially for MEPI, which indicates that the presence of

288 chlorine substituents has a deep impact on the enantioresolution. The nature and
289 position of the substituents in Am1 and Cell1 are identical, however better resolution
290 values were obtained with Am1, especially for PRILO. The inclusion of a chlorine atom
291 at position 3 instead of a methyl group in Am3, compared with Am1, resulted in a slight
292 improvement in resolution for BUPI and MEPI, but a worsening for PRILO and
293 PROPA.

294 When it comes to the mobile phase, ACN as organic modifier provided, in most
295 cases (see Tables 2 and 3), better enantioresolution than MeOH. However, the complete
296 resolution of the BUPI enantiomers was only achieved using MeOH in the mobile phase
297 (70 %) and the Cell3 CSP. For this compound, in most cases, the use of ACN did not
298 provide any enantioseparation; only partial resolution was achieved for the Cell2 CSP.
299 It is also worth mentioning the excellent resolutions obtained for the enantioseparation
300 of PRILO using the Am1 CSP and both MeOH and ACN as organic modifiers. The
301 value of R_s value of 9.5 for the mobile phase consisting of MeOH: ammonium
302 bicarbonate buffer (5 mM, pH 8) 90:10 (v/v) is by far the highest value obtained. In
303 general, resolution improved as the percentage of ACN or MeOH decreased; for
304 instance, for PRILO and MEPI in Cell2 using ACN, or PRILO using MeOH in Am3
305 (see Tables 2 and 3). However, in the case of BUPI in Am3 and MeOH as organic
306 modifier the opposite behavior was observed; the values of resolution were better when
307 using higher proportions of MeOH in the mobile phase.

308

309 *3.2. Chiral chromatographic analysis*

310 Table 4 indicates the chromatographic conditions selected for each analyte to
311 complete the chiral analysis of the samples in the subsequent biodegradability assays.

312 These conditions were chosen considering both the enantioresolution and the retention
313 times of the compounds obtained during the optimization process (see Tables 2 and 3).
314 For BUPI and MEPI, the values of temperature and mobile phase flow rate were
315 adjusted to obtain the most convenient conditions in terms of resolution and speed of
316 analysis. Figure 1 shows the chromatograms for the four local anesthetics obtained
317 using the selected chromatographic conditions. The chromatograms correspond to some
318 of the samples taken during the biodegradability assay. In Figure 1A, the chromatogram
319 corresponding to the (*S*)-enantiomer of BUPI was included for identification purposes.
320 In all cases, adequate separations were achieved in less than 12 min.

321 Methodological calibration for each enantiomer was performed under the
322 chromatographic conditions selected. The calibration curves were obtained by injection
323 of standard solutions containing the racemic compound in the 1-30 mg L⁻¹ range (5
324 concentration levels) (see section 2.1). Table 4 shows the calibration statistics obtained
325 for each enantiomer. Satisfactory results were obtained for the enantiomers of the four
326 local anesthetics studied ($R^2 > 0.99$).

327 The confidence intervals for a 95% confidence level for the intercepts included
328 the 0 value, which means that the values of b_0 are statistically equal to 0 (assumption
329 made in Eq. 1). These results proved the validity of the approach based on the direct use
330 of the areas of chromatographic peaks to estimate the *BD* values in the present study.
331 The slopes (b_1) of both enantiomers for PRILO and PROPA are statistically equal
332 (assumption made in Eq. 2), so the *EF* values could also be calculated using the direct
333 chromatographic approach. However, for BUPI and MEPI, the values of b_1 were not
334 statistically equal, and therefore, the *EF* could not be calculated directly from the
335 chromatographic peak areas, so concentration values were used instead.

336 According to the “fit-for-purpose concept”, full method validation of the current
337 analytical method becomes unnecessary [28]. First, the method was not designed for
338 routine sample analysis. Second, to obtain the biodegradation data, the estimation of
339 concentrations is not necessarily required, since it is possible to use directly the peak
340 areas measurements. Besides, performance features and quality assurance parameters of
341 the same procedure have been established elsewhere for two drugs [22], and substantial
342 differences are not expected.

343 3.3. Biodegradability assays

344 The OECD ready biodegradability tests have been thought as screening methods
345 to determine whether a substance is or not potentially easily biodegradable or not
346 [26,27]. The biodegradability assays for the enantiomers of local anaesthetics were
347 performed in batch mode by duplicate (Section 2.3). Samples were incubated and
348 collected at different times ($t = 0, 3, 7, 14$ and 28 days) for the biotic and abiotic assays
349 and analysed in the optimal chromatographic conditions (Table 4). Fluoxetine (FLX, 20
350 mg L^{-1}) was tested in parallel as reference substance to ensure the adequate activity of
351 the microbial community in the test system [28]. According to the criteria established in
352 a previous paper, if the biodegradation (BD) values after seven days of incubation
353 (BD_{7d}) are within the $70 \pm 11\%$ range, the inoculum biodegradation capacity could be
354 considered as normal. In the present case, a BD_{7d} of $69 \pm 12\%$ for FLX was obtained,
355 indicating the adequacy of the inoculum and thus, the validity of the assays. The activity
356 of the inoculum was also monitored by measuring the optical density at 600 nm .

357 Figure 1 shows for each analyte two chromatograms corresponding to biotic
358 samples taken at $t = 0$ and 28 days. For BUPI and MEPI, there were only slight
359 differences between the samples, which indicates a poor degree of degradation under
360 the conditions assayed. Conversely, in the case of PRILO, there was a significant

361 decrease in the peak areas of both enantiomers after 28 days of incubation. This
362 decrease was even greater for PROPA, which was completely degraded during the assay
363 (there were no peaks in the corresponding chromatogram, Fig. 2D). No appreciable
364 differences between the areas of the chromatographic peaks of both enantiomers were
365 observed for any compound, suggesting the non enantioselectivity of the processes
366 involved in the degradation of the local anaesthetics.

367 Figure 2 shows the *BD* values obtained during the biodegradability assays for
368 the enantiomers of local anaesthetics (left part) as well as the corresponding *EF* (right
369 part). The initial concentration of each enantiomer (S_0) was approximately 10 mg L⁻¹.
370 Both BUPI and MEPI presented low values of biodegradation during the whole
371 biodegradability assay. For the enantiomers of BUPI and MEPI, the maximum
372 estimated degradation after 28 days of incubation in the biotic assay was approximately
373 10 % and 15 %, respectively. Regarding the abiotic assay (in the absence of inoculum),
374 the degradation at the end of the test was around 5-10 % for the enantiomers of both
375 compounds. These results indicate that both, the biodegradation and the
376 physicochemical degradation can be considered non-significant [26,27]. According to
377 the criteria established in the OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and
378 Development) guidelines, BUPI and MEPI enantiomers would not be readily
379 biodegradable and could be considered as potentially persistent compounds. As
380 expected due to lack of biodegradation, the values of *EF* remained constant and close to
381 0.5 (Figure 2) during the biodegradability assays.

382 For both enantiomers of PRILO, the maximum estimated degradation at 28 days
383 of incubation was approximately 69 % and 23 % in the biotic and abiotic assays,
384 respectively. These results indicate that PRILO enantiomers exhibit incomplete but
385 appreciable degradation, not only physicochemical but also microbiological ($BD - D >$

386 20 %). In the case of the enantiomers of PROPA, the complete degradation was
387 achieved in only three (or less) days under biotic conditions. In the abiotic assay, the
388 degradation remained not significant ($D < 20\%$) until $t = 14$ days, which points out the
389 major contribution of the microbiological biodegradation to the degradation process.
390 After 28 days of incubation, the values of degradation in abiotic conditions reached 53
391 %, indicating that even in the absence of microorganisms, this compound is easily
392 degraded by physico-chemical mechanisms.

393 According to the results obtained and the OECD guidelines [26,27], it can be
394 concluded that PROPA and PRILO enantiomers exhibit ready aerobic biodegradability.
395 For both PRILO and PROPA, the *EF* values remained close to 0.5 throughout the
396 biodegradability assay, indicating the prevalence of non-enantioselective mechanisms in
397 the degradation processes.

398

399 **4. Conclusions**

400 The comprehensive study on the chiral separation of bupivacaine, mepivacaine,
401 prilocaine and propanocaine with eight polysaccharide-based chiral stationary phases in
402 reversed phase conditions compatible with MS detection revealed that when using
403 aqueous- MeOH mobile phases a typical reversed phase behaviour, i.e. the retention of
404 compounds increased as the proportion of organic modifier in the mobile phase
405 decreased. When ACN was used as organic modifier, for all the columns and
406 compounds, the retention of compounds initially decrease for low water content in the
407 mobile phase (HILIC behavior). while at the higher content (up to 20 %(v/v) of water
408 content) in the mobile phase retention increase (reverse-phase behavior). This explained
409 effect is more evident for the column Cell3, Cell5 and Am1 for MEPI and PROPA.

410 In the conditions assayed, none of the columns provided the enantioseparation of
411 the four compounds studied. The polysaccharide-based CSPs tested presented different
412 enantioselectivity towards the analytes. The Cell2 CSP allowed the baseline resolution
413 of the enantiomers of mepivacaine, prilocaine and propanocaine. The Cell1, Am2 and
414 Am3 CSPs were not able to completely resolve the enantiomers of any of the
415 compounds. Except for bupivacaine, the use of acetonitrile as organic modifier in the
416 mobile phase instead of methanol provided better resolution values. In general, the
417 resolution increased as the retention increased. As far as we know, no references for the
418 chiral separation of local anaesthetics in reversed phase conditions compatible with MS
419 detection using polysaccharide-based stationary phases exist for bupivacaine, prilocaine
420 and propanocaine.

421 The adequate mobile phases for the separation of the local anaesthetics studied
422 were used to perform an enantioselective biodegradability study. Under the conditions
423 tested, the enantiomers of bupivacaine and mepivacaine were not significantly
424 degraded, so they can be considered potentially persistent. On the contrary,
425 propanocaine and prilocaine exhibited ready biodegradability. No enantioselective
426 biodegradation was observed for any local anesthetic studied. As far as we know, this is
427 the first study on the enantioselective biodegradation reported for these compounds.

428

429 **Conflicts of interest**

430 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

431 **Acknowledgments**

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537

538 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

539

540 **Figure 1.** Chromatograms of (A) bupivacaine, (B) mepivacaine, (C) prilocaine and (D)
541 propanocaine obtained by HPLC-MS using the experimental conditions detailed in
542 Section 2.2. Chromatograms 1 and 2 correspond to samples containing racemic
543 mixtures at $t = 0$ and $t = 28$ days of incubation, respectively. Chromatogram 3
544 corresponds to a standard solution of (*S*)-bupivacaine. Initial racemate concentrations
545 were 19.8, 20.6, 21.0 and 21.0 mg L⁻¹ for BUPI, MEPI, PRILO and PROPA,
546 respectively.

547

548 **Fig. 2.** Biodegradation (*BD*, %, mean \pm s from two replicates) calculated from peak
549 areas using the Eq. (1) and enantiomeric fraction for (A) bupivacaine, (B) mepivacaine,
550 (C) prilocaine and (D) propanocaine by HPLC-MS. (○) *BD* for E1, less retained
551 enantiomer; (Δ) *BD* for E2, most retained enantiomer; (●) *EF*.

552